

SIGNIFICANCE OF RESIDUAL CURING STRAINS IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURE REPAIR TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

The Structures and Materials Laboratory is engaged in developing generic technology for the repair of composite aircraft structures. As a preliminary task, a suitable specimen geometry for static and fatigue related testing of graphite/epoxy laminates is being developed. This report describes the use of a photoelastic coating to measure strain patterns surrounding machined holes in laminates. This technique also identified and quantified the residual stresses. These stresses are inherent to the multidirectional laminates and may be partially released during machining operations.

INTRODUCTION

The Structures and Materials Laboratory of the National Aeronautical Establishment (NAE) is undertaking a research project dealing with the repair of damaged graphite/epoxy composite structural components typical of the CF-18 fleet of aircraft. These materials take the form of monolithic laminates for upper and lower wing skins or thin face sheets of sandwich type structures representative of those found on vertical and horizontal stabilizers.

In the development of this repair technology, the characterization of damage severity is important. The form of damage of particular interest is a "through-thickness" hole. Work carried out at NAE by Raizenne et al.[1] investigated the effects of through-thickness hole diameter on far field failure strains. In that work, it was found that for a given specimen width, the relationship between hole diameter and failure strain was non-linear. This suggested that further investigation of the strain patterns surrounding through-thickness holes was required. A specimen geometry, based on the above work was selected for this study.

SPECIMEN PREPARATION AND TEST SET UP

A single 29.5" x 7" (750x178mm) specimen was machined from an AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy panel. The 44 ply lay-up is representative of an area of the lower wing skin of a CF-18 and consists of 27.3% 0° plies, 54.5% 45° plies and 18.2% 90° plies. The nominal cured thickness of the specimen was 0.23" (5.84mm).

A photoelastic coating (Measurements Group type PS-1) was bonded to one side of the specimen. The chosen coating thickness was 0.080" (2mm), with a fringe value $f = 915 \mu\text{strain per fringe}$. Only one side was coated since the stiffness of the coating relative to that of the specimen is negligible. Due to symmetry, it would have been sufficient to cover only 1/4 of the specimen with the coating. However, it was undesirable to have the coating edge coincide with the strain concentration point therefore the photoelastic coating was extended to cover 3/4 of the specimen.

The specimen was configured in three different geometries for testing as follows:

- (I) as prepared, shown in Figure 1
- (II) with a 2" (50.8mm) diameter center hole, shown in Figure 2
- (III) with a 2" (50.8mm) hole scarfed out to 4" (101.6mm) on the uncoated face of the specimen, shown in Figure 3

Figure 1. Specimen Configuration I. All numbers in brackets are in millimeters.

Figure 2. Specimen Configuration II. All numbers in brackets are in millimeters.

Figure 3. Specimen Configuration III. All numbers in brackets are in millimeters.

A set of friction type grips designed at SML was used for testing. The specimen was restrained in the grips using large C type clamps. A pair of steel shims was inserted into each grip and both the shims and the specimen grip ends were lightly sand blasted to produce a dull surface in order to maximize the friction effect.

The specimen was loaded in an MTS 880 system load frame with a capacity of 100,000 lbf (445kN).

Photoelastic effects were observed with a reflection polariscope, Model 030, from Measurements Group. The fractional isochromatic fringe values were measured with a Soleil-Babinet compensator. Fringes were recorded on Ectachrome 400 ASA

slide film as well as on video tape. The use of video equipment and a monitor allowed all personnel involved in conducting of these tests to observe fringe changes "in real time" and also proved to be invaluable for reviewing the tests on frame by frame basis.

An MTS Model 632.11B-20 extensometer (1" (25.4mm) gauge length) was used for comparison of strain results.

METHOD: PHOTOELASTIC COATINGS

Photoelastic coatings have been applied successfully to isotropic materials for more than 30 years and comprehensive monographs on this method have been published [2],[3].

The first strain data for composites obtained using a photoelastic coating method were published in the late 60's by Dally and Alfirevich [4]. Later Pipes and Dalley performed a more in-depth investigation of the application of photoelastic coatings to composites [5]. A good review of several cases of photoelastic coating studies on composites can be found in Reference [6].

The photoelastic coating method is a variation of two-dimensional photoelasticity whereby the birefringent material is bonded directly to the tested component rather than being used to produce a model. The reflection polariscope is used to measure the birefringence caused in the coating due to the specimen deformation. Two families of lines can be observed: the isochromatics and the isoclinics. The isochromatics are lines of constant shear strain while isoclinics are lines on which the directions of principal strains are constant.

The equation of an isochromatic can be written as:

$$\gamma = \epsilon_1 - \epsilon_2 = f \cdot N \quad (1)$$

where f - is isochromatic fringe value

N - is fringe number

ϵ_1, ϵ_2 - principal strains

Frequently the isochromatic pattern provides sufficient information to the experimenter. However, if normal strain magnitudes are required, additional effort is necessary to obtain this information. Strain separation, as this effort is referred to in photoelasticity, can be done either experimentally using oblique incidence [7], separation gauges, slitting techniques or numerically [2-3]. All strain separation techniques are time consuming although improvements have been realized using computer based methods involving image processing. Since this capability is not yet available at the Structures and Materials Laboratory, strain separation on a full field basis was not attempted in this project. However, in some areas of the specimen the stress state could be regarded as unidirectional therefore the principal strains in these locations are related to each other through Poisson's ratio:

$$\epsilon_2 = -\nu \cdot \epsilon_1 \quad (2)$$

In some instances of application of photoelastic coatings to composites, the birefringence observed at the edge of the coating is distorted by the mismatch of Poisson ratios between the coating and composite materials and requires corrective calculations. For this particular specimen, the Poisson ratio was $\nu = 0.36$ [1] which was very

close to that of the coating $\nu = 0.38$, hence the strains could be easily separated along the edges. It should be noted that this match of Poisson ratios was quite incidental, but fortunate.

RESULTS

Figure 4. Birefringent effect caused by residual stresses in graphite/epoxy.

The tests carried out on specimen configuration (I) (without the hole) have shown that care is needed in the installation of the specimen to avoid introducing bending or twisting loads. As well, it was observed that the influence of gripping extended about 3" (75mm) from the grip edge which left a uniform strain field of about 16" (400mm) in length as indicated by a uniform fringe value. As the stress field in this area was uniaxial, the equation given in the previous section was used to estimate strain levels for various applied load levels. The calculated strains were within 1% of strains measured with an MTS extensometer.

Figure 5. Specimen in configuration II loaded to 30,000 lbf (133.4 kN).

After machining a 2" (50.8mm) diameter hole, specimen configuration (II), compressive strains were observed around the hole edge. This strain effect is shown in Figure 4 and it was approximately 447 μ strain which is significant as it is over 10% of the ultimate design strain limit of 4000 μ strain. This residual strain effect has not been previously reported because the holes in specimens were machined prior to the photoelastic coat application.

Specimen configuration (II) was loaded to 30,000 lbf (133.45 kN). The isochromatics were photographed through a monochromatic filter so that the high order fringes at the hole could be recorded. Figure 5 shows the complete isochromatic field near the hole. The isochromatic readings indicate an approximately 2" (50.8mm) wide zone where strain

could be treated as "far field" between the grip and the hole. The stresses in the far field zone and at the hole edge are unidirectional so the principal strain can be calculated using following formula derived from equations (1) and (2):

$$\epsilon_1 = f \cdot \frac{N}{(1+\nu)} \quad (3)$$

To calculate the strain concentration factor (k), isochromatic fringe readings were taken using a compensator in the far field zone (N_f) and at the hole edge (N_h). The reading at the hole edge was increased by the isochromatic residual compressive strain reading (N_r) taken before the specimen was loaded. Using equation (3) it can be shown that k can be calculated from the following formula:

$$k = \frac{\epsilon_h}{\epsilon_f} = \frac{(N_h + N_r)}{N_f} \quad (4)$$

Using the formula, the strain concentration factor was estimated to be 3.76.

Figure 6. Birefringent effect caused by residual stresses observed after machining of the scarf.

At this point, a scarf was machined at the specimen hole to represent configuration (III) (Figure 3). The scarfed hole resulted in a complex isochromatic pattern from the release of the residual stresses from the curing process during the machining operation (Figure 6). It should be noted that the scarf area represents an unbalanced laminate and closer examination of this zone indicated in-plane and out-of-plane deformation of the hole edge. Second order isochromatics can be seen in the scarfed zone indicating the existence of shear strains of up to 1830 μ strains. The design ultimate strain limit for

graphite/epoxy composite primary structure is typically 4000 μ strains. While this limit applies to normal strains, a strain field involving shear strains approaching 50% of the ultimate design strain allowable must be considered in the design of composite repairs.

When the specimen was loaded, it was observed that the far field strain zone had reduced in size and that the grip strain field and the strain field associated with the hole began to interact. This might lead to the conclusion that a longer specimen should be used. It should be remembered, however, that this specimen is to be used for the evaluation of composite repair techniques by comparing strain fields before the repair, as in configuration I and II, and after repair with a bonded patch in the scarfed area. The scarfed hole itself represents a condition which would not normally be subjected to loading. Small scarfed holes are prevalent for fastener countersinks and for those cases the effect of residual strains on load induced strain field should be investigated.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

1) Residual stresses inherent to multidirectional laminates cured at high temperatures may have significant influence on composite repair techniques.

2) The decision as to the specimen length should be made only after complete stain analysis of a patched hole configuration.

3) Photoelastic coating is an inexpensive, real time, full field technique which can be very effective in specimen development.

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